
Issues of Increasing Tax Revenues by Improving Tax Risk Detection Mechanisms

Abdurasulov Alisher Abdurasulovich

Researcher at TSUE

Abstract: Among tax indicators, the tax risk indicator is of great importance. Based on the correct assessment and determination of this indicator, it is possible to reduce the risk of taxpayers' tax evasion. The correct determination of the criteria for the tax risk indicator also involves complex relationships in this process, which requires constant improvement. This article discusses the directions for the correct determination of the criteria for the tax risk indicator in the tax system and its improvement.

Key words: tax risk, criterion, tax revenues, tax system, tax indicators, tax debt, efficiency of the tax system, tax, collection, tax period, tax relations, tax elasticity, principles of taxation, tax legislation.

Introduction.

In terms of content, it is advisable to divide the risks themselves into two groups. The first group is natural and technical problems that are difficult to assess in advance, and the management of such risks and the prevention of their negative consequences depend on the level of scientific development. Although it is possible to identify social risks, the level of their consequences is much higher than natural, technical and economic risks, and their elimination is much more difficult. Economic risks, although they are considered social in nature, are somewhat more difficult to assess, identify the factors of their origin, and manage, but are much softer than natural risks. It should not be forgotten here that the complex objective laws of the economy and the form and content of economic relations make it difficult to assess economic risks. This requires the study of the most optimal methods of managing economic laws and relations.

Economic risks are the degree of negative impact of emerging threats in the economic sphere, and in order to more fully determine their essence, we consider it methodologically correct to distinguish their characteristic features. One of the characteristic features of economic risks is their basis in risk taking. As recognized in many literatures, risk taking is the action of economic individuals as a result of their economic decisions, which ultimately lead to risks, and as we noted above, risks are economic conditions and processes that have an impact.

One of the tax indicators is the tax risk management system. In recent years, a new system in the tax system of Uzbekistan or one of the tax indicators being analyzed is the introduction of the tax risk management system in tax authorities. In world experience, the tax risk management system (CRM - Compliance Risk Management) in the management information system of the State Tax Administration is an advanced international practice, and its place and role are becoming increasingly important.

It should be emphasized that scientific research on ways to increase tax revenues by identifying tax risks is not sufficiently comprehensive, and therefore requires strengthening scientific research in this area.

Literature review.

Scientific research on the issues of increasing tax collection through the correct identification and assessment of tax risks has taken place in the scientific research of scientists involved in tax relations. In particular, this problem has been addressed to some extent in the scientific research of Stigler G. Spencer H., Schutz A., Luckman T., Johnson, S., Kaufmann, D., Shleifer, A., Goldman, M.I. & Weitzman, M.L., Balabanov I.T., Blank I.A., Bublik D., Dyatlov S.G., Graboviy P.G., Efimov S.L., Ivanyan A.G., Kalashnikova E.L., Krylatykh E.N., Kineev Yu., Lavrushin O.I., Leushev A.A., Lipnik L.G., as well as domestic scientists F.Mirzaev, F.Akhmedov, M.Elbaeva. Today, there is a growing need for research related to reducing taxpayers' tax liabilities and preventing tax evasion through tax risk assessment.

Research methodology.

In carrying out research on the problems of increasing tax collection through the correct identification and assessment of tax risk, methods widely used in scientific research methodology are also used. If deductive or inductive methods are used to reveal the essence of the relationship between tax indicators, then grouping, synthesis and analysis methods are effectively used to analyze the factors affecting it. In addition, based on statistical analysis, economic and tax indicators, including the dynamic changes in the impact of tax risk on other tax indicators, are analyzed, in which widely used research methods are widely used.

Analysis and results.

Determining the tax risk allows the state tax service to implement tax control while reducing the intervention of taxpayers' activities and encourages to take administrative measures to increase the collection of taxes as much as possible. In practice, in order to fully determine the tax risk, the activity of taxpayers is segmented and the potential tax risk is determined, its level is assessed by conducting a tax risk analysis, and the tax risk is determined. Based on them, tax risk management mechanisms are implemented.

The problem of identifying and eliminating tax risks, as the most urgent problem in the tax system, is an integral part of the activities of state tax authorities. Controlling them requires the implementation of a wide range of measures. Systematically, identifying tax risks covers the entire process from segmenting taxpayers' activities to determining tax control measures.

One of the most difficult aspects of tax risk assessment is the process of identifying potential tax risks, and the criteria used to determine the risk play a crucial role in determining this. In determining these criteria, the characteristics of taxpayers in terms of paying taxes are important. To get a general idea of the main tax types and the criteria for calculating VAT, we present Figure 1 below.

Figure 1. Some criteria for determining the tax risk for value added and profit tax ¹.

As is known, the taxes with the most complex mechanisms in the tax system are VAT and income tax. Therefore, in determining tax risk, we will focus on the analysis of these two types of taxes and the criteria used to determine them.

As shown in Figure 1 above, the criteria for determining the tax risk are different for them, and they are determined based on the characteristics of taxation and the determination of the tax base. Some of the listed criteria serve to determine the tax risk of double taxation in the same order. For example, the following criteria are used as criteria for determining the tax risk on profit: analysis of the correct reflection of the amount of VAT not taken into account according to the VAT report in the profit tax expenses, criteria such as comparing the indicators of income from the operating lease of property in the profit tax and VAT reports, comparing the indicators of the profit tax and VAT reports of the net income from the sale of products, and in the way of determining the tax risk in terms of VAT applied criteria: comparison of value added tax and profit tax indicators, comparison of value added tax and EHF indicators can be used to determine the tax risk of both

¹ Compiled by the author.

taxes. This compatibility of tax risks is characterized by the fact that both types of taxes are primarily related to the cost of products and expenses.

Table 1. Analysis of tax risks identified based on the application of tax risk criteria for profit and value added tax

№	Tax risk indicators	Types of taxes					
		Profit tax			Value added tax		
		2021 ӳ	2022 ӳ	2023 ӳ	2021 ӳ	2022 ӳ	2023 ӳ
1	Tax risk determined on the basis of the criteria introduced into the "Avtokameral" software product						
	Number of criteria	24	18	21	31	25	28
	Amount of difference (billion soums)	11650,2	8316,5	9568,4	4965,2	3580,8	6547,2
2	Tax risk arising from financial reporting indicators						
	Number of criteria	11	9	7	7	5	12
	Amount of difference (billion soums)	4368,4	3970,0	4641,2	2258,2	1916,8	2278,2
3	Tax risk arising from tax reporting indicators						
	Number of criteria	13	9	14	24	20	16
	Amount of difference (billion soums)	7281,8	4346,5	4927,2	2707	1663,9	4296,0

The conclusions of the tax risk analysis determined based on the application of tax risk criteria for profit and value added tax can be summarized based on the table above, which shows that different criteria were applied in the tax risk analysis determined based on the criteria implemented in the "AutoCameral" software product in the years under analysis. For example, if this program used 21 criteria for profit tax in 2023, the amount of differences determined based on the application of 28 criteria for VAT amounted to 9568.4 billion soums and 6547.2 billion soums in 2023, respectively. If we pay attention to the differences in tax risks determined based on financial and tax reporting indicators for these two types of taxes, we can conclude that the amount of tax risks for income tax amounted to 7,281.8 billion soums in 2021, and decreased by 2,354 billion soums in 2023 to 4,927.2 billion soums. This means that the amount of tax risks has decreased and the number of cases of tax evasion among taxpayers has slightly decreased.

Conclusion

As a general conclusion, it can be said that, firstly, determining the tax risk indicator based on its results, officially warning taxpayers and allowing them to correct it, creates the opportunity to carry out tax control without excessive interference in their activities; secondly, identifying tax risk and reducing its negative impact is a qualitatively meaningful and important economic factor for increasing tax collection; thirdly, the highest level of tax risk by tax type is found in VAT and income tax, the main reasons for this are the large number of factors that contribute to the emergence of tax evasion in these types of taxes and their connection with costs; fourthly, due to the large number of criteria for determining tax risk, changes in the economy and the entry of enterprises into economic relations and the expansion of new types of economic activity, it will be necessary to constantly expand these criteria and revise the existing ones in terms of economic

efficiency; fifth, it is necessary to improve the mechanisms for determining the methodology of determining the tax risk.

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